

Figure S3. AntiSYS inhibits the high-affinity systemin receptor SYR1 but not the low-affinity SYR2.

Non-shared letters indicate groups with statistically significant differences.

- (A)** 1-way ANOVA on aligned rank-transformed data, performed separately for *N. benthamiana* + SYR1 and *N. benthamiana* + SYR2:
- for *N. benthamiana* + SYR1: $F_{3, 28} = 57.4$, $P = 4.5 \times 10^{-12}$
 - for *N. benthamiana* + SYR2: $F_{3, 28} = 3.4$, $P = 3.3 \times 10^{-2}$ (no significant differences in *post-hoc*)
- each followed by *post-hoc* ART-C contrast tests with *P*-value adjustment acc. to Tukey and $P_{adj.} < 0.05$.

- (B)** Welch's ANOVA, performed separately for treatment groups of *N. benthamiana* + SYR1 and *N. benthamiana* + SYR2:
- for *N. benthamiana* + SYR1: $F = 143.0$, $df = 4$, $P = 3.4 \times 10^{-11}$
 - for *N. benthamiana* + SYR2: $F = 92.8$, $df = 4$, $P = 6.3 \times 10^{-10}$
- each followed by *Games-Howell post-hoc* test, with *P*-value adjustment acc. to Benjamini-Hochberg, further adjusted for repeated testing on these subsets of data by the same method, and with $P_{adj.} < 0.05$.

